

Data citation and publication by the UK's Natural Environment Research Council's data centres

Sarah Callaghan (1), Nathan Cunningham (2), Mark Thorley (3), Roy Lowry (4), Gwen Moncoiffe (4), and the NERC Data Citation and Publication Project Team
(1) British Atmospheric Data Centre, STFC, UK (sarah.callaghan@stfc.ac.uk), (2) Polar Data Centre, British Antarctic Survey, UK, (3) NERC, UK, (4) British Oceanographic Data Centre, UK

Why publish data?

Scientific journal publication mainly focuses on the analysis, interpretation and conclusions drawn from a given dataset. Examining the raw data that forms the dataset is more difficult, as datasets are usually stored in digital media, in a variety of (proprietary or non-standard) formats.

Therefore, peer-review is generally only applied to the methodology and final conclusions of a piece of work, and not the underlying data itself. But if the conclusions are to stand, the data must be of good quality. The peer-review process ensures the quality of the work reported in the journal article, while the publication process produces an article which is fixed and citable, and provides its author(s) with academic credit.

Benefits to the community

A process of data publication, involving peer-review of datasets would be of benefit to many sectors of the academic community.

Data scientists have to ensure that the data are of high quality and that the associated metadata and documentation are complete and understandable. This leaves little time for the analysis of the data required to produce a paper suitable for journal publication. Publishing a dataset in a data journal will provide academic credit to data scientists, and without diverting effort from their primary work on ensuring data quality.

Funding organisations want to get the best possible science for their money. Running measurement campaigns is expensive, so the more reuse that can be derived from a dataset, the better. Publication in a data journal ensures that the dataset is uploaded to a trusted repository where it will be backed up, archived and curated and so won't be vulnerable to bit-rot or being lost/stored on obsolete media. The peer-review process also reassures the funder that the published dataset is of good quality and that the experiment was carried out appropriately.

Publication demonstrates to the wider research community that the datasets are reliable and complete, and therefore the data can be trusted.

Data journals will be a good starting point for information for researchers outside the immediate field, about what sort of data is available and how to access the data. This will encourage interdisciplinary collaboration, and open up the user base not only for the datasets, but also the data journal and the underlying repositories.

The availability of published datasets will make it easier to validate conclusions through the reanalysis of those datasets.

Data publication will help show transparency in the scientific process, improving public accountability.

The NERC data centres, and examples of the wide variety of data stored in our repositories.

Aims of the project

The UK's Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) funds six data centres which between them have responsibility for the long-term management of NERC's environmental data holdings. The NERC Science Information Strategy (SIS) has been created to provide the framework for NERC to work more closely and effectively with its scientific communities in delivering data and information management services.

- To increase NERC's influence on work to provide and cite data outputs from scientific work in similar ways to scientific papers.
- To implement publication and citation of datasets held within the NERC data centres.
- To form partnerships with other organisations with the same goal of data publication to exploit common activities and achieve a wider community buy-in. To this end, project team members are involved with both the SCOR/IODE/MBL WHOI Library Data Publication Working Group and the CODATA-ICSTI Task Group on Data Citation Standards and Practises.

The wider win is to the research integrity of NERC's data. Data citation and publication will ensure that data is available, peer-reviewed, citable, easily discoverable and reusable; and it facilitates data transparency and scrutiny. It will be used by researchers to increase their academic status, thereby providing encouragement for them to archive and document their data appropriately, for the benefit of the wider research community.

Citation or publication – which comes first?

In traditional academic publishing, the object to be cited (i.e. the article) is written and peer-reviewed before it becomes citable. In the case of data publication, it makes more sense to allow citation of the dataset before full peer-review. If scientific peer-review of a dataset is considered the "gold standard", citation therefore becomes a "silver standard", confirming that the dataset is complete, unlikely to change, in an appropriate format and has sufficient metadata (at least as far as the host repository are concerned).

The Mechanics of Citation

What sort of data can we cite?

The cited dataset has to be:

- Stable (i.e. not going to be modified)
- Complete (i.e. not going to be updated)
- Permanent – by assigning a DOI we're committing to make the dataset available for posterity
- Good quality – by assigning a DOI we're giving it our data centre stamp of approval, saying that it's complete and all the metadata is available

When a dataset is cited that means:

- There will be bitwise fixity
- With no additions or deletions of files
- No changes to the directory structure in the dataset "bundle"

What citing mechanism will we use?

Citing mechanisms already exist for some of the data stored in the NERC data centres, e.g. life science identifiers, fossils in the Paleosaurus database. To cite other digital objects we decided to use digital object identifiers (DOIs) because:

- They are actionable, interoperable, persistent links for (digital) objects
- Scientists are already used to citing papers using DOIs
- Existing data journals and repositories such as Earth System Science Data (ESSD) and Pangaea already use DOIs to link to the datasets they publish.
- The British Library gave us an allocation of 500 DOIs to assign to datasets as we saw fit as part of their DOI for data pilot project.

What rules will we apply to our data citations?

A DOI should point to a html representation of some record which describes a data object.

- Upgrades to versions of data formats will result in new editions of datasets (and therefore new DOIs).
- DOIs will resolve to human-readable landing pages which contain a link to the location of the data files. These landing pages can be from the data centre's catalogue, or can be an OAI-ORE aggregation.

Landing pages

- Landing pages can have query based links to other things (papers which cite this dataset) etc ...
- Landing pages can be changed as required, but the (DOI-mandatory) metadata describing the dataset shouldn't change because:
 - It describes the digital object and represents it faithfully. It ought not change, since any change to it, ought to reflect a change to the digital object (which should trigger a new DOI)
 - and the original landing page can indicate that a newer version of the dataset exists, but it should still point to the older version!

Example landing page from the BADC metadata catalogue

Thanks to the British Library for providing the DOI minting account and DOI allowances to allow this project to cite datasets held in the NERC repositories.